

Review

Importance of Nanoparticles, Synthesis, Characterization and its Applications in the New Era of Research

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Abstract In nanoscience, there had a wild place of Nanoparticles, because of their Nanostructure, complex reactivity and solidity. In this work we have circled the Importance of Nanoparticles in our daily life and their routine synthesis in laboratories, but also discuss the extended (Green) method for synthesis of Nanoparticles which were approachable to the environment. By acquainting with different methodologies for the characterization of Nanoparticles and their applications in field of Nanoworld has discussed.

Keywords Nanoparticles, synthesis

Introduction

Material with a typical diameter of less than 100 nm is Known as nanoparticles [1]. Nanoscience is a significant field of synthesis dealing with modern research, strategy, and use of particle's structure ranging from roughly 1-100nm. Entirely the properties within this size range (physical and biological, chemical) changes for both individual of atoms/molecules in fundamental ways and their comparable bulk. Innovative applications of the nanoparticles and nanomaterials are increasing speedily on several fronts due to their entirely new or improved properties built on size, their morphology, and distribution. In a large number of fields, it is rapidly gaining renovation such as health care, biomedical, cosmetics, drug-gene delivery, food and feed, health, environment, chemical industries, space industries, optics, light emitters, nonlinear optical devices, single electron transistors, mechanics, electronics, energy science, photo-electrochemical, catalysis and countless applications. Prodigious growth in these growing technologies had opened novel fundamentals and applied frontiers. This contains the invention of

nanoscale materials afterward in search of their mysterious physical and optical properties [2-4]. All the purposes mentioned above the nanoparticles used, and the metallic nanoparticles considered as the most capable due to their large surface area to the volume ratio they contain notable antibacterial properties, which is of attention for researchers due to the increasing microbial resistance against metal ions, development of resistant strains and the antibiotics [2]. In recent years there is much interest taken in the field of nanoscience as in fig: 1 shows that the no of publications, thus increasing interest in nanoparticles because of their unique properties which differ significantly from those of the bulk material.

Types of nanoparticles

In the field of nanoscience, there are many nanoparticles are being synthesized with differing size, shape, compositions, and functionalities. Such as,

Iron oxide nanoparticles

Iron (Fe) oxide nanoparticles are broadly considered as a passive and active directing imaging agent as they are showing mainly superparamagnetic properties.

The superparamagnetic Iron (Fe) oxide Nanoparticles (SPIONs) generally contain iron oxide core with a hydrophilic coat, made of dextran or another bio-compatible compound to enhance their stability [5,6]. The commonly used SPIONs consist of maghemite ($\gamma\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) as well as magnetite (Fe_3O_4) core. These particles display superparamagnetism which is size-dependent and it tolerates them to become magnetized with the applications of the external magnetic field and it will show zero net magnetization upon removal of the net magnetic field. Fe nanoparticles

containing zero-valent Fe and Fe oxides that can act as a catalyst for the removal/degradation of organic solutes [7-9].

Presently, two SPIO agents are clinically permitted for MRI, ferumoxides with size 120–180 nm and ferucarbotran with size 60 nm. SPIONs by using different methods it can be functionalized with magnetic, radionuclide, optical and with specific targeting ligands. Furthermore, the particles with nanometer sized metal oxides are not target selective for samples which have complex matrices. That's why; an appropriate coating is required to overcome such limits in a complex matrix. To overcome such problem, physical or chemical changes on/in the sorbent surface with specific organic compounds, particularly chelating agents with binding sites, are frequently used to load the surface with donor atoms such as nitrogen, oxygen, phosphorus, and sulfur [11,12]. These chelating agents are capable of selective binding with specific metal ions. They can also use as drug delivery carriers [13].

2. Gold Nanoparticles

Gold nanoparticles have different size and shape which depends on chemical properties, optical bio-compatibility and superficial surface variation [14]. Due to exclusive interaction between free electrons of Nanoparticles and light, the Gold nanoparticles can sturdily improve the optical processes such as light absorption, scattering, fluorescence and surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) [15]. Due to such properties, the gold nanoparticles have various uses in field of biology, such as biological imaging, diagnostics, biochemical sensing and the detection, and biological applications. The Gold nanoparticles use in Sensing techniques including colorimetric arrays, and also use as substrates in SERS to significantly improve Raman scattering, which allow for spectroscopic findings and identifying proteins and single molecules at the nanoparticle surface [16]. Gold nanoparticles probes have also been used in heart disease and cancer biomarkers [17] [18].

3. Silver nanoparticles

Silver is cheaper but less common than the gold. It is harder metal but can be extremely ductile and as well as malleable. Silver possess additional thermal and electrical conductivity than all other metals with lowest resistance. In electrochemistry Silver has great importance, it is used in reference and counter electrodes, as electrical contact material in the manufacture of different electrodes and silver also use as a paint for printed electrical circuit. In the air and water Silver is

stable, but get tarnishes when it exposed to ozone, hydrogen sulfide, and also in air containing sulfur [19]. For the detection of hydrogen peroxide, Macro silver electrodes can be used [20, 21], sulfide, cyanide, iodide and bromide [22] and other organic compounds including enzymes [23, 24], DNA [25] and hemoglobin [26]. Well bulk silver show catalytic activity for hydrogen peroxide through different methods, such as, autocatalysis [21] and oxide layer formation [20]. There are many ways to produce Silver nanoparticles, for example via microemulsions [27] and organometallics [28]. There are several methods but, the main methods to produce silver nanoparticles for use in electrodes have been direct electrodeposition onto a substrate surface or the evaporation of colloidal silver.

4. Quantum Dot

Quantum dots also well known as fluorescent semiconductor nanocrystals (QDs) are semiconductor particles with size less than 10 nm in diameter. QDs show exclusive size dependent optical and electronic properties [29]. More than a few characteristics distinguish QDs from the usually used fluorophores. Colloidal semiconductor quantum dots are a few nanometers in single diameter crystals whose size and shape can be just controlled by the duration, temperature and ligand molecules that used in synthesis [30]. QDs have essential advantages for optical applications over many organic fluorophore dyes. QDs used in the biological research as a fluorescence imaging applications for example, biomolecule tracing and cell classification [31-33]. The small size of QDs also allows them to be fit for biomedical applications such as, diagnostics and medical imaging [34].

5. Targeted nanoparticles

The idea of targeting nanoparticles has become important attention in medical research in fresh years. Monoclonal antibodies and the development of small molecules in the areas of drug discovery and molecular therapeutics have significantly altered the cancer treatment. NPs display much potential in therapeutic applications. In certain, NPs have many exceptional properties that improve or confer benefits over the current methods in biological and biomedical research. Therefore, it has been noteworthy attention in applying the targeting ideas to design NP. This can be achieved by active targeting as well as passive targeting under *in vivo* conditions [35].

Synthesis of nanoparticles

Through different methods Synthesis of Nanoparticles can be achieved. The most widely used chemical approaches for the production of Nanoparticles are Vapor-phase synthesis [36], sol-gel synthesis [37], Hydrothermal Synthesis [38], precipitation method [39], sonochemical method [40], solvochemical synthesis [41], microwave method [42], Template method [43] mediated method [44] and chemical reduction method [45] etc. Though, still some chemical methods use of toxic chemicals that cannot avoid in the synthesis procedure. Subsequently the nanoparticles such as gold, platinum and silver nanoparticles are broadly useful to human contacting areas, so there is a growing requirement to develop environmentally friendly procedures of nanoparticles synthesis that avoid the use of toxic chemicals. The biological approaches for Nanoparticles synthesis using the enzyme [48], microorganism [46–47], and plant extract have been proposed as conceivable green changes to physical and chemical methods. It can also be appropriately grownup for large scale synthesis of the nanoparticles [49]. This carried on the synthesis of basic metallic nanoparticles of silver and gold by the reduction of Au^{3+} ions and Ag^+ ions with Neem leaf broth (*Azadirachta indica*). Through this method 90% reduction of Ag^+ ions and Au^{3+} ions were performed using Neem leaf and time period required was about four and two hrs respectively, the Green synthesis of Fe Nanoparticles is evolving as a method that would impact on the steric stabilization of Fe nanoparticles against aggregation and help to overcome the agent in daily reported synthesis. Recently, for the successful Synthesis of Fe Nanoparticles, the green tea leaf and sorghum bran extracts have been reported so far [50-52]. well in this work, Fe nanoparticles were synthesized by using green tea leaf extracts. Green tea contains polyphenols that act as a reducing agent as well as a capping agent.

Characterization of nanoparticles

Characterization of nanoparticles can be achieved by different techniques, through that we can able to know their sizes, shapes, stability and their morphologies. most important techniques which are being used for characterization of NPs are given such as, Raman spectroscopy [53], UV-visible spectroscopy [54], Infrared spectroscopy [55], X-ray Diffraction (XRD) [56], Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) [57], Mass spectroscopy (MS) [58], (TEM) Transmission electron microscopy [55], (SEM) Scanning electron microscopy [56], Fluorescence spectroscopy [59], Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) [60], Small-angle Neutron Scattering (SANS) [61], (NSOM) Near-Field Scanning Optical Microscopy [62], Circular Dichroism (CD)

[63], (DSC) Differential scanning calorimetry [64], (TGA) Thermal gravimetric analysis [65] and Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) [66].

Applications of nanoparticles

An applications list of some of the nanomaterials is given below:

- Drug and gene delivery [67, 68]
- Bio-detection of pathogens [69]
- Fluorescent biological labels [70, 71, 72]
- Detection of proteins [73]
- Tissue engineering [74, 75]
- Probing of DNA structure [76]
- Tumor destruction via heating (hyperthermia) [77]
- Cancer therapy [78]
- Removal of metals [56]
- Degradation of organic pollutants [79]
- Removal of dyes [80]
- Electrochemical Sensors and Biosensors. [81]

Conclusion

Here we can see that how the NPs have a wide range of applications and can be synthesized by different methods, and can be characterized by various techniques. These NPs are the backbone of the future research. In the coming few decades NPs contribute the primary role in technology and biology especially in the field of cancer treatment being used as a drug carrier.

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